

Towards personal data store-based retrieval augmented generation in mobile computing

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Abstract. Conversational AI agents have the potential to dramatically improve human ability to interact with the digital world. However, this is currently limited by data sharing between disparate application domains. A decentralized data exchange based on personal data stores can exist for applications to enable knowledge integration across these domains. Knowledge graphs and vector embeddings are critical to scale this behavior. In this work, we create and evaluate a prototype mobile-based retrieval augmented generation architecture based on personal data stores.

Keywords: Conversational AI · Decentralization · Retrieval Augmented Generation · Mobile Computing.

1 Introduction

The attention mechanism that underlies current large language models (LLMs) was first described in 2014 [7] and extended in 2017 into the transformer architecture [27]. The Bidirectional Encoder Representation for Transformers (BERT) extended the large language model landscape [10] and decoder-only models such as the Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) [22] have continued to improve the state-of-the-art through architecture improvements and infrastructure improvements to increase the number of trainable parameters. The transition of LLMs from the pure research domain to more general use is a significant moment in computing. Training an LLM on an individualized basis is currently infeasible. It has been reported that the GPT-4 model costs \$100 million [15]. Context-driven mechanisms such as “retrieval augmented generation (RAG)” [16] have been developed to allow for LLMs to communicate more individualized information. RAG has the potential to dramatically improve mobile-device interaction by realizing the idealized context-aware computing paradigms envisioned since Weiser’s seminal paper on ubiquitous computing [30].

One major concern towards realizing this vision is data fragmentation preventing efficient RAG computation. Data fragmentation exists as a result of both technological constraints and data ownership challenges, requiring a fundamental change in the way mobile devices store data for disparate applications. Centralization of data per application is the de facto standard in Web 2.0. Large web-applications serve many clients, while client devices connect to different web

applications for each service that is needed for computation. A semi-solution can exist through mirroring all client device data from centralized stores to an intermediate location for RAG computations. This approach is dependent on each application allowing data extraction and results in data duplication in the best case, and the potential for intentional data manipulation by third parties in the worst.

This paper considers a fully decentralized alternative, which is depicted in Figure 1. The figure depicts the network-connected flow, where the user (1) authenticates their data access, and are provided an access token (2). They access their personal data store (3) to retrieve documents which are sent to the RAG service (4) which computes using either a property graph or vector database (5). The resulting query is sent back to the mobile application through a notification service (6). For the no network flow, the application kicks off a local RAG service which uses an embedded vector database and more limited LLM to provide query responses.

Mobile applications store data in personal data stores using context-rich data descriptors, and applications share data between clients through linked-data paradigms. The advantage of this data architecture is that there is no additional requirement or condition to enable RAG interactions from personal mobile devices. However, each mobile application is then responsible for storing data in ways that RAG can effectively make use of that information and knowledge to improve LLM interactions. We explore this through a pilot study using Solid [24] as the personal data store standard, and investigate the use of knowledge graphs and vector embeddings from personal data stores to achieve better interactions with mobile LLM agents.

In this pilot study, we conduct early experimentation for Solid-based mobile RAG interactions. Specifically, we investigate 1) server-side and mobile-native query execution, 2) vector-database and knowledge graph execution, and 3) re-indexing strategies. These experiments are aimed to inform future research in pursuit of fully decentralized data approaches to mobile LLM interaction.

2 Related Work

The Solid Protocol is an effort to decentralize the World Wide Web [24]. Specifically, they aim to re-imagine the underlying data architecture [19] in order to create a Semantic Web to support personalized AI agents [8]. The main com-

Fig. 1. The proposed architecture for our mobile-centric RAG service using decentralized datastores.

ponent to provide support for the decentralization aspect are personalized data stores (“Solid Pods”). These Solid Pods provide private storage related to a users’ data which they can manage themselves through security [1] and identification protocols [2]. This storage and access control structure is ideal to apply retrieval augmented generation (RAG) models and aligns with the original intent for personalized agents. Research in this area has already shown some promising results [28]. Our work aims to augment existing research through enabling semantic RAG using Solid onto mobile devices.

Semantic approaches to mobile computing have had limited success due in part to resource constraints as well as data centralization tendencies. The maturation of semantic web technologies and the Solid protocol has resulted in recent research in mobile decentralization. Mobile devices interacting with Solid Pod servers has been demonstrated in several applications, including 1) a mechanism to map requests from different applications to a server on a mobile device in order to improve recommendations across multiple apps [14], 2) a way to use of your phone as a personal data store to improve advertising [13], and 3) an application which integrates Solid and Google’s Health API to personalize and store fitness and health data[21]. However, there is no previous work on an intersection of RAG and the Solid protocol for mobile devices.

Despite being a nascent field, LLMs have been the focus of many computer science researchers, resulting in significant progress. The GPT-family of models has entered common vernacular, but comparable models (e.g. LLama [12]) have also shown significant utility. Many of the improvements have been made through increasing the number of trainable parameters and clever architectural improvements including chain-of-thought. These improvements have been met with some concerns including hallucination [31]. One popular approach to handling hallucinations and other shortcomings of LLMs is Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)[16]. RAG applications have grown in popularity, and been shown promise in several domains including mobile devices for resource optimization [23] and show further optimizations where frozen LLMs fall short[20].

Knowledge graphs are a potential alternative to vector databases for indexing and retrieval. These can be obtained from the web [4] or constructed using encoder models [32]. There is the potential for knowledge graphs to outperform vector databases as suggested in recent work [11]. RAG has been extended into mobile computing. However, an open question is whether offloading this computation is more effective, and we demonstrate the ability to delegate queries to your personal data store with a property graph index to answer queries with better performance, falling back to the on-device vector store model when network connectivity is limited or unavailable.

Another quickly growing area of research is using LLMs to critique text, referred to as “LLM-as-a-judge” [17]. LLM-as-a-judge is used for contextual evaluation instead of traditional scoring methods like ROUGE, BLEU, and METEOR which match a reference answer sequentially. In our experiment, we selected Qwen13 with 14B parameters in thinking mode as the judge. While it is intuitive that a larger model may perform better than a smaller model, research

shows a model with good reasoning capability can compare with the state-of-the-art models [9]. We also created a custom rubric for our judge, which has shown to improve evaluation performance [18].

3 Methodology

To test our idea, we developed a prototype architecture leveraging Solid personal data stores (Pods) as the storage for multiple client applications. To prevent exposing private personal data and allow for reproducibility, our test data is composed of hand-selected text data from Wikipedia. We use graph transformers in tandem with LLMs to construct knowledge graphs. These knowledge graphs are used as the source for the LLMs to perform retrieval-augmented generation to address user queries.

Dataset selection: To construct the graphs, we chose six articles related to the life of Charles Darwin. This included information regarding his advisors, published works, and personal life. We initially constructed three knowledge graphs using the same graph transformer approach and Gemma 3[25] Instruction Tuned model with 1B parameters, referred to as “gemma3-1b-it“. These graphs were each constructed using all six documents in increments of two, starting with the initial two documents and the final graph consisting of all six documents.

Dataset subselection: These knowledge graphs provide a good initial test. In real-world scenarios, decentralized applications will listen to resources which are “living” (e.g. blog entries, social media posts), which is data that should be indexed to improve mobile LLM interaction. Through this living interaction paradigm, the resources will updated with new information in the form of structured and unstructured documents. A question which follows is *“how will the construction of an index initially with a graph transformer from unstructured text perform compared to an index which is initially constructed with less data, and later receives additional context from a resource notification?”* To address this question, we created three more knowledge graphs, consisting of two initial documents, then adding two more to the index at runtime and comparing to their statically constructed equivalent—e.g. the four document database compared to the two document database with the next two documents dynamically added to the index. This resulted in three knowledge graphs dynamically creating consisting of 2+2, 4+2, and 2+2+2 dynamic document indexes.

Query generation: To construct queries, we used a transformer API to provide chunked documents which then produced reference questions, answers, and the context from which queries were generated. The generation was performed by chunking and generating three queries per chunk for each document separately, then in the same increments of two for building the databases. The queries were generated using both gemma and Microsoft’s Phi4[3] model (9B parameters), referred to as “phi4“. After generating the queries and metadata, they were combined and filtered to retain the first instance of each unique question—e.g. Q1 appears in Set 1 and Set 5, the question is kept from Set 1 (earliest appearance). This mechanisms yielded 1200 potential queries, which were filtered (e.g. removing duplicates). The remaining 800 queries were separated into documents consisting of the document clusters—all questions from Document 1, Document

2, and the combination of Document 1 and Document 2 were placed into one set. This resulted in 5 clusters with 50-350 questions per document. The difference in sizes is due to the variable length of the referenced documents, mimicking real-world qualities of living documents. Finally, the quality of the output from the query generator was variable. To provide more robustness, and validate that queries were proper questions, we filtered all of the queries to ensure they ended with a “?” character. We then randomly sampled a subset of forty queries per document testbed, resulting in 120 total unique queries.

Android RAG Vectorization: To generate the data for the Android RAG model, the documents were chunked using three different approaches. The model used on the Android device was Gemma3-1b-it with int4 quantization. This is slightly different from the model used for testing as the local Gemma model knowledge graph does not perform int4 quantization. To compare our gemma model and the Android provided gemma model, we compared the responses from queries to determine their similarity and performance, which should provide better validation and expectations for comparing the performance of a model support by a vector store and a model supported by a knowledge graph.

To set up the Android experiment, we assembled a sample application which chunks the documents and ingests the queries loaded into the assets folder. The resulting vector store contains 1024 embedding dimensions against which queries are executed and the responses are recorded. We then compared these results with the responses from our local Gemma model.

Model Comparisons: To compare the results of two models, we leveraged LLM-as-a-judge through the Qwen3[26] model with 14B parameters. The LLM-as-a-judge was constructed using a custom prompt and output metric to validate the responses with respect to their context chunks and the reference answers generated by the RAG dataset generator. One caveat to note is that LLM-as-a-judge is an emerging area of research and strategies for comparison from differently generated sources have not been solidified. The resulting LLM-as-a-judge model is a simple pairwise evaluator which compares the corresponding responses from two models and judges their response with respect to a rubric and the generated reference answers. Previous research has demonstrated that changes to the prompt can result in different responses and judgments of answer quality, and the corresponding answers may be biased or opinionated based upon the prompt[29]. In future work, we would like to establish a baseline of human-sourced opinions of the responses to provide few-shot prompting to the RAG system and to establish a human ground truth as well as validate that the custom judge scores match the expectations provided in the prompt.

4 Results

Our prototype system was capable of performing RAG interactions for mobile devices leveraging data from personalized data stores. The prototype system consists of a Python application on the backend [5] and the Android application [6]. For execution time (As shown in Table 1), the vector database strategy was the

quickest, including round-trip network time. Property graph was faster than the Android strategy. The computational limitations of the Android device (Pixel 6A) being a primary concern for both execution and query response accuracy. For response quality (shown in Table 2), the Server-backed vector-store-based RAG strategy outperformed the other strategies in the LLM as a judge metric when using the full dataset. The base LLM outperformed the Android LLM without RAG strategy due to the more computationally capable models. The property graph was slightly better than the Base LLM

strategy. The Android RAG with vector database outperformed the base Android LLM in selection percentage and average score from our custom prompt. Finally, our analysis of the “living” quality of documents was inconclusive regarding the accuracy of reindexing strategies for both the property graph and the vector database strategies. Our expectation was that property graphs would better facilitate this interaction, and future work can identify whether this is true, especially for personalized data that cannot have been indexed by the base LLM strategy.

5 Conclusion

In this work, we introduce and evaluate a retrieval augmented generation pipeline that leverages a decentralized mobile application paradigm to improve interactions with large language models. Informed through our methodology and evaluation, we anticipate that a trend towards data decentralization has the capacity to greatly improve context aware computing for mobile devices, and that knowledge graphs may have significant impact in allowing for continual dataset reindexing as information is added.

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Table 1. Comparison between execution time for RAG strategies

RAG Strategy	Query Execution Time (s)		
	Average	Median	Std Dev
Server Property Graph	12.4	9.25	6.7
Server Vector Db	4.99	4.01	3.40
Android Vector Db	27.6	28.2	20.1
Android Vector Db w/ Docs	9.8	6.3	10.9
Network Time	0.68	0.68	0.07

Table 2. LLM-as-a-judge response selection for RAG strategies

RAG Strategy	Pairwise Selection (%)			
	Base LLM	VS	PG	ALLM
Base LLM	N/A	22.5	40.1	55.3
Server Vector Store (VS)	73.9	N/A	63.7	80.7
Server Property Graph (PG)	47	32.7	N/A	N/A
Android Base LLM (ALLM)	31.5	16	N/A	N/A
RAG Strategy	Selection (%)	Avg. Score	Std Dev	
Android Base LLM	32.7	0.451	0.216	
Android Vector Database	60.2	0.601	0.273	

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